

Risks and Resilience of Cultural Heritage Assets

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Abstract. The heritage assets are permanently exposed to natural and anthropogenic hazards. The risk analysis which are the among the most important tools needed for decision making in process of cultural heritage asset management and maintenance is quantitative and qualitative. The qualitative part is in case of heritage assets more demanding than quantitative. However, the basic questions are related to prediction of type of harmful event, likeliness of its appearance and prediction of its consequences. In this process is important to identify the potential risks for heritage asset under observation and capacity of asset to resist the potential harmful impacts. The starting point of activities in process of sustainable protection of cultural heritage asset is collecting of as much as possible complete set of data where the use of contemporary and emerging ICT tools is unavoidable. In the present paper the contributions of recently completed FP7 projects Climate for Culture and EU CHIC as well as ongoing H2020 project INCEPTION will be presented and highlighted in context of risks and sustainable protection of cultural heritage assets. Both the problem of objects and buildings will be addressed and protocols for data collecting developed in above named FP7 projects will be described.

Keywords: cultural heritage, risks, resilience, data collection protocol, 3D digital documentation

1. INTRODUCTION

The European and Mediterranean built heritage is endangered by environmental impacts that are becoming more and more severe due to climatic changes. However, the additional serious threat to heritage is simply lack of knowledge of subjects that are engaged in its safeguarding even on the basic level of relatively simple but extensive interventions in building structure and fabrics. In September 2009, the 36 months European Coordinated Action entitled European Cultural Heritage Identity Card was launched. Its main intention was to establish the Pan-European approach to collection and evaluation of data on cultural heritage assets in order to facilitate the increase of knowledge on the heritage building stock across Europe. It is needed as a support of sustainable maintenance and preservation and revitalization of historic sites and monuments in general. The concept of the Identity Card of heritage buildings and monuments is description and classification system for data collection on current state of asset including available data about the asset changes over time. It is essential for development of the management, conservation and maintenance strategies.

In many countries there are well-established systems and tools used for inventory and documentation of the cultural heritage. The tradition in care for cultural heritage reflects in them and the local approaches and understandings are basis for their approach to content. In some countries there are several systems for data collection, which are not connected together. Therefore, the strait comparison of data on heritage assets is not possible. The overview of currently used

approaches in seven countries (Croatia, Czech Republic, Greece, Israel, Italy, Poland and Slovenia) was presented during the 1st EU-CHIC Workshop held in Vienna on April 29 2010 (Žarnić et al., 2012). However, the Ad hoc group for Inventory and Documentation within the Technical Co-operation and Consultancy Programme related to the Integrated Conservation of the Cultural Heritage contributed the most complete effort in harmonization of approaches on at least basic level in form of three standards related to historic buildings, monuments, archaeological sites and heritage objects (Guidance, 2009).

The idea of Identity Card originates from the COST Action C5: “Urban Heritage-Building Maintenance”, 1996-2000 (Hofmann et al., 2002). The general conclusion stressed in final report was that there is a serious lack of reliable data on European urban heritage and a pressing need to collect it, in order to support the on-going process of refurbishment of existing buildings. COST C5 Action concluded that there are great variations in the systems of establishing and evaluating data from buildings in the European countries. The responsibility for collecting data depends on the administrative structure in each country. Planning of broad activities, such as preventive strengthening or even post-earthquake measures in European earthquake prone areas, or energy preservation measures, can be better based on mutually developed methodology. The basic rules and approach can be developed from the existing European standards and codes. However, no generally accepted approach existed that would lead to European methodology.

The creation of Pan-European protocol for data collection is just a first step in the more ambitious process. The essential part of data in this protocol is related to identification of risks to which heritage assets are exposed. It is well known that the vulnerability of assets is one of main criteria for intervention in asset in order to increase its resilience. The final aim of process is to develop a general approach to resilience assessment of heritage assets based on identification of risks that can be generalized by introduction of risk indicators.

2. THE CULTURAL HERITAGE IDENTITY CARD

The main objective of the Coordinated Action EU-CHIC (www.eu-chic.eu) was to develop and test guidelines that are required for the efficient compilation and storage of data pertinent to each asset under observation. The current trends in heritage preservation are oriented to sustainable maintenance, preventive conservation, and rehabilitation of historic sites and monuments. They also include newly developed strategies of efficiency evaluation, and creation of user-friendly methodologies for screening of time varying changes to heritage buildings as a result of human intervention and environmental impact. The basis of all above mentioned activities and approaches is wide knowledge about heritage assets that can be obtained only by systematic collection and proper processing of data. Data can be collected and well maintained only if the appropriate protocols are developed and applied. In figure 1 the main purpose for establishing of documentation protocol is briefly illustrated.

Fig 1: The role of documentation protocol in process of heritage preservation

The documentation protocol can be understood as an envelope with set of rules, which establish and define the categories of data needed for achievement of targeted goal. If protocol is set in general way, it can be used for collection and processing of different types of data. In case of protocol for cultural heritage it can be applied to build heritage, to archaeological sites, to cultural landscape, to heritage objects and to collections of artefacts. Protocol can be composed of several layers regarding the type of data their amount and nature. During their lifetime the heritage assets have been constantly exposed to external natural influences that caused the material and structure decay processes and to alternations of use and interventions in their structure. The necessary data for evaluation of consequences of events in assets lifetime can be collected from different sources and documents but the on-site inspection is the only way to assess the current state of asset. From assessment of asset under observation and knowledge gained from studying of similar cases the prediction of future behaviour can be estimated. The important data for estimation, besides ones collected by inspection, are risks of events that may happen in future life of asset. The sufficient amount and reliability of data is necessary background for decision-making that determines and thus influence the future life of asset. Those who are responsible for asset should always be ready to answer to the simple question: "What will be the consequences of their decisions?"

The collecting of detailed data on cultural heritage assets engage a significant amount of efforts of professionals and researchers what means also engagement of significant amount of funds. Therefore, the owners or responsible organization of authority has a property rights and can exploit data following their needs. However, a certain amount of data should be given to the interested public for general use (research, education, tourism etc.). On other side, the sensitive data that are under owners' control are needed for management and all other decisions related to ownership of asset.

As an answer to these dilemmas, the new structure of data has been developed. It was visualized in form of iceberg and named "Chicberg" (figure 2).

Fig 2: The "Chicberg" scheme of data organization

Table 1: Data categories in the “Chicberg” scheme

General Data: Basic information o cultural heritage asset			
Name, location, legal status, type, dating, function, major risks, materials, structure, state of conservation			
Pool of Knowledge: Detailed Information on the Cultural Heritage Asset			
Non-physical Aspects		Physical Aspects	
History	Legal issues	Geospatial aspects	Structure
Art history	Economical issues	Risks	Movable objects
Sociology	Previous interventions	Archaeology	Current condition
Ethnology	Conservation	Architecture	Energy efficiency
Cultural landscape	Valuation methods	Materials	Surveying techniques
Decision Support: Knowledge implementation procedures			
Intervention decision making			
Decision impact analysis			
Site management			

Data, that in their total volume create the Identity Card, are divided in two groups (table 1). The “upper” group of data are open to general, public use. The “lower” two groups of data are the sensible ones and of high value for owner of asset. Therefore, they can be used only upon their permission.

Following this scheme, the Cultural Heritage Identity Card is not a single document of asset but a set of documents that contains comprehensive information and that are created and updated due entire lifetime of asset. The updating follows the changes of asset after the initial creating of files. Therefore, the system of three levels is established as presented in table 1. The first level of the Card contains data collected mainly from publically available sources with additional information about current physical condition and major risks to which asset may be exposed. The original intention of the Card was to establish a system that will enable comparison between the assets of same type across the Europe and Mediterranean countries. The first level of the Card is designed to meet this goal.

When designing the first level of card the existing national and international systems were carefully studied to include some of their parts into it. Ad hoc Group for inventory and documentation within the Technical Co-operation and Consultancy Programme within the Council of Europe has developed the most comparable system that is divided in three internationally agreed standards for the documentation of the cultural heritage: “Core Data Index to Historic Buildings and Monuments of the Architectural Heritage”, “International Core Data Standard for Archaeological Sites and Monuments” and “Object ID” (<http://archives.icom.museum/object-id/heritage>).

The standards form an important, well-established system and the intention of EU CHIC is not to compete or replace it but to integrate them to wider and more ambitious system. The first level of the Card is meant as an introduction to lower, more important levels because the basic information about asset given in the first level is elaborated in detail in the second level named Pool of Knowledge. The structured knowledge, as presented in table 1, is a basis for the most important aim of system: support to decision making that is of crucial importance for preservation of cultural heritage asset. One of most important issues is prevention of heritage asset from the risks. Risks can be identified from past events in area of heritage asset location but also from the scientific prediction of potential harmful events. The variety of risks and concurrency of events can be managed by introduction of risk indicators that enable good prediction of influences even when the amount of reliable data is not sufficient. Using data collected at the second level, the resilience of heritage asset can be assessed as explained in next chapter of this paper.

3. RISK, VULNERABILITY AND RESILIENCE OF HERITAGE ASSETS

3.1 *Risk and resilience in general*

The concepts of vulnerability, resilience and risk are relatively well established in many disciplines related to environment and its protection. Some of these elements can be used in the domain of cultural heritage preservation. What is missing is an action that will gather the existing knowledge, contribute to existing knowledge with concrete tools for quantification of risk indicators, promote their application, and communicate the outcomes through workshops and conferences.

The research networking within the group of experts will further upgrade the Cultural Heritage Identity Card by widening the aspects of risks and development of common resilience models of built cultural heritage. Its development will continue in the HORIZON 2020 project INCEPTION (www.inception-project.eu), where several partners of EU CHIC projects are involved.

Because of vast number of built heritage assets across Europe, it is fairly impossible to cover all assets. This issue can be addressed to a certain extent through development of risk indicators, which requires clear rules and protocols for collecting and managing data on various types of heritage assets and related risks. Referring to the OECD approach to measurement, a risk indicator is an indicator that captures the potential for some form of resource degradation using mathematical formulas. Risk indicators are particularly useful as they reduce the number of parameters that would otherwise be needed to reflect the actual situation. To communicate clearly with concerned stakeholders, the pertinence of risk for heritage, the scope of a selected indicator set and the level of detail need to be limited. Otherwise, an extensively broad set would clutter the specific information it is meant to provide. In their interpretation, the risk indicators need to lend themselves to unambiguous division into combining parts. Such decomposition into sub-components of a risk indicator is necessary to understand the impact of underlying factors on the aggregate picture that a risk indicator presents. Due to their adaptation to user needs for the right information for the right purpose, indicators may not necessarily meet strict scientific demands to demonstrate causal links. Risk indicators rather highlight key trends and correlation patterns that provide basis for further research based on appropriate mathematical models to establish causal relationships.

In general, the selection of risk indicators will ideally need to be based on clearly defined general and specific criteria. Generally speaking, the risk indicators will need to be relevant for informing about the resilience of heritage to pressures induced by humans and nature. Specific risk-heritage links will also need to be measurable and quantifiable by accurate and timely data, which are available at a reasonable cost. The analytical soundness of the methodology to construct indicators is of essence here.

Another set of specific criteria is required to reflect the vulnerability and resilience aspects in relation to cultural heritage assets, defined as follows:

- Risk indicator is an indicator that estimates the potential for some form of heritage asset degradation using mathematical models.
- Vulnerability of heritage asset is a measure of the extent to which it is likely to be damaged due to the location, nature or the impact of a particular disaster hazard.
- Resilience of heritage asset is its technical capacity to respond with resilience to external perturbations and changes or to a particular disaster hazard.

The proposed unified approach to monitoring risks to cultural heritage will also allow scientifically based prioritization of interventions. Currently, the selection of most needed actions is difficult because relevant data are scattered across countries, there is lack of clearly defined criteria, and shortage of available funds for individual initiatives in countries. The countries partnering in the INCEPTION project will therefore benefit from the access to the proposed system for identification of risks to heritage assets. It will provide them with the opportunity to apply the proposed set of indicators in planning of maintenance and preventive conservation activities.

Table 2: Major risks to which are heritage assets exposed

Environmental risks				
Long term influences			Sudden events	
Bio attack	Solar radiation		Wind-storm	Landslide
Climate conditions fluctuations	Particle matter and aerosols		Fire	Avalanche
Aeolic impact	Long term influences		Flood	Tsunami
Water impact (ground, atmospheric)	Geological conditions (global, local)		Earthquake	Volcano
Anthropogenic - social risks				
Unintentional influences			Intentional events	
Economic activities			Vandalism	
Accidents			Riots	
Improper decisions			Wars	

Major risks that affects the asset, as identified within the EU CHIC project, are presented in table 2 above. Long-term environmental impact is expressed in term of the environmental factors, which affect the asset and the results appeared after a long period of time. Sudden environmental impacts are expressed in terms of events which affect the asset and which time of occurrence could not be foreseen in advance. Anthropogenic impacts that might be the consequence of regular economic activities and other unintended sources of harmful influence to heritage asset or the consequence of intended harmful influences. Among the most dangerous are the improper decisions of those who are responsible for management of asset.

3.2 Resilience model for heritage assets

The concept of resilience is developed in domain of earthquake engineering, but earthquake is only one of sudden environmental impacts that endanger heritage buildings. However, the knowledge developed in this area can be transferred and enlarged to all other risks to which heritage assets are exposed. As part of the conceptualization of a framework to enhance the seismic resilience of communities in USA (Bruneau, M. et al., 2003), seismic resilience has been in 2003 defined as the ability of a system to reduce the chances of a shock, to absorb such a shock if it occurs (abrupt reduction of performance) and to recover quickly after a shock (re-establish normal performance). More specifically, a resilient system is one that shows:

- Reduced failure probabilities,
- Reduced consequences from failures, in terms of lives lost, damage, and negative economic and social consequences,
- Reduced time to recovery (restoration of a specific system or set of systems to their “normal” level of functional performance)

Fig 3: Resilience model (a) proposed by Bruneau M. et al., 2000 and resilience model of cultural heritage asset in the case of long term (a) and in the case of sudden (b) environmental or/and anthropogenic-social impacts (proposed by authors of this paper)

A broad measure of resilience that captures these key features can be mathematically expressed and thus calculated. Resilience depends on the quality of the asset. Specifically, performance can range from 0% to 100%, where 100% means no degradation in quality and 0% means total loss. If an earthquake or other disastrous event that occurs in short time period, it could cause sufficient damage to the asset such that the quality measure is immediately reduced (from 100% to 50%, or in the worst case of collapse to 0%). Restoration of the asset is expected to occur over time it is completely repaired and functional (indicated by a quality of 100%).

When the resilience of existing, contemporary infrastructure endangered by earthquakes is observed (figure 3a), the basic assumption is that the infrastructure is 100% resilient in time of occurrence (t_0) of earthquake and that the same resilience can be restored by appropriate intervention in certain time period (t_1).

The assumption of here proposed resilience model for cultural heritage assets (figure 3b and 3c) is different because of the specific nature of cultural heritage asset. It was 100% ($R_0 = 1$) resilient in time of its creation. Various long-term and sudden impacts occurred during its lifetime that is measured by centuries or even millenniums. In present time (t_1) in figure 3b, is the resilience of asset much lower than the initial one ($R_1 < R_0$). It practically cannot be completely restored to its original state but only to best achievable ones ($R_1 < R_2 < R_0$). Theoretically it would be possible to reach the initial resilience (R_0) only in cases, when the complete documentation of the initial state would be available. Documentation is complete only if contains both, data on tangible characteristics and intangible values of asset. The solution of problem becomes even more demanding if in observed, present time (t_1) in figure 3c the additional sudden drop (R_e) of resilience occurs during the natural or anthropogenic-social impact.

Extended research is needed to quantify resilience, particularly for some type of critical assets. For critical assets for which the deliverable is not a simple engineering unit, such as for the case of heritage endangered by anthropogenic threats the quantification is almost impossible. However, it is worthwhile to start research in this area, which is completely new, and the future progress and outcomes are not very much predictable.

Resilience for both physical and social systems can be further defined as consisting of the following properties (Bruneau M. et al., 2003):

- Robustness: strength, or the ability of elements, systems, and other measures of analysis to withstand a given level of stress or demand without suffering degradation or loss of function.
- Redundancy: the extent to which elements, systems, or other measures of analysis exist that are substitutable, i.e., capable of satisfying functional requirements in the event of disruption, degradation, or loss of functionality.
- Resourcefulness: the capacity to identify problems, establish priorities, and mobilize resources when conditions exist that threatens to disrupt some element, system, or other measures of analysis. Resourcefulness can be further conceptualized as consisting of the ability to apply material (i.e., monetary, physical, technological, and informational) and human resources in the process of recovery to meet established priorities and achieve goals.
- Rapidity: the capacity to meet priorities and achieve goals in a timely manner in order to contain losses, recover functionality and avoid future disruption.

In the specific cases of heritage assets additional properties should be identified.

3.3 Resilience and risk indicators

The basic idea of further research in cultural heritage domain is to apply theory of resilience for development of efficient measures for preservation of cultural heritage assets. It is obvious that for each type of environmental or anthropogenic impact the mathematical models of resilience should be developed but, all will emerge from the above explained platform (figure 3). The main problem is not in mathematical formulation of model but in reliable and realistic input data for calculation of resilience. In case of heritage asset that is exposed to several different catego-

ries of impacts, the total resilience is a combination of partial resiliencies associated with every relevant impact. And as mentioned above, the earthquake is only one of them.

The use of the risk indicators for definition and, where it is possible, quantification of input parameters for resilience assessment is crucial for practical application of resilience model. In principle, indicators can serve many purposes depending on the level at which they are applied, on the audience to be reached, and on the quality of the underlying data sets.

A key function of indicators is to simplify the communication process by which the results of analysis and accounting are provided to the users and to adapt information to their needs. The indicators need to be communicated in a way that is understandable and meaningful by reducing the complexity and level of detail of the original data. Due to this simplification and adaptation, the indicators may not always meet strict scientific demands to demonstrate causal chains. They rather represent trade-offs between their relevance for users and policies, their statistical quality and their analytical soundness and scientific coherence. Indicators therefore need to be embedded in larger information systems – such as databases, accounts, monitoring systems and models.

Although some of these categories of risks as presented in table 2 above can be quantified, such as earthquake risk, there is no generally accepted measurement framework that would permit standardized description, harmonized monitoring, and analytically sound quantification of risks to built heritage assets. However, an additional risk to those ones presented in table 2 should be mentioned - a risk of deteriorating processes in materials and structures relate to external influences or internal chemical and/or physical time-depending variations of material characteristics. A dashboard of risk and resilience indicators would facilitate prediction of the long-term natural impacts and management of anthropogenic factors.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In current era of rapid development of ICT their application in heritage preservation domain is not yet sufficient. However, the international interest for using of ICT tools in traditionally and by its nature conservative discipline is growing. Very positive move in this direction has been achieved during the International Conferences on Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries EUROMED 10, 12 and 14 (www.euromed2012.eu and www.euromed2014.eu) where the large area of possibilities and already developed technologies and applications in cultural heritage domain were presented. The architecture of EU CHIC is opened for further upgrading what gives opportunity for rising of its quality by wide application of ICT. But the main role of ICT will be in providing data and models for resilience assessment using the risk indicators. As stressed earlier, the quality and quantity of reliable documentation is crucial for restoring of resilience of heritage assets. Important part of documentation is visualization of asset as whole and its parts including details that may have a crucial importance in restoring of monuments and historic buildings. The long-term preservation of data is another crucial issue that has to be still addressed on proper way. The current storage media may not be sufficiently durable and resistant to various influences. Therefore, new media should be developed and become available in order to assure long-term preservation of stored data. The ongoing H2020 project INCEPTION will contribute to the development of resilience models by extensive development of crucial ICT tools.

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